

1 Nested cross validation Gaussian Process to model Dimethylsulfide mesoscale
2 variations in warm oligotrophic Mediterranean seawater
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14 **Abstract**

15 The study proposes an approach to elucidate spatiotemporal mesoscale variations of seawater
16 Dimethylsulfide (DMS) concentrations, the largest natural source of atmospheric sulfur aerosol,
17 based on the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) machine learning model. Presently, the GPR was
18 trained and evaluated by nested cross-validation across the warm-oligotrophic Mediterranean Sea, a
19 climate hot spot region, leveraging the high-resolution satellite measurements and Mediterranean
20 physical reanalysis together with in-situ DMS observations. The end product is daily gridded fields
21 with a spatial resolution of $0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$ (~9 km) that spans 23 years (1998–2020). Extensive
22 observations of atmospheric methanesulfonic acid (MSA), a typical biogenic secondary aerosol
23 component from DMS oxidation, are consistent with the parameterized high-resolution estimates of
24 sea-to-air DMS flux (F_{DMS}). This represents substantial progress over existing coarse-resolution
25 DMS global maps which do not accurately depict the seasonal patterns of MSA in the
26 Mediterranean atmospheric boundary layer.

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Accurate estimation of sea-to-air dimethylsulfide flux (F_{DMS}), the largest natural source of sulfur
29 aerosol particles in the atmosphere, requires a reliable prediction of seawater dimethylsulfide
30 (DMS) concentration. DMS is a volatile biogenic gas produced by marine microorganisms that,
31 when released into the atmosphere, influences the formation of aerosols and affects cloud
32 properties¹⁻³ and consequently planetary albedo and climate⁴. Many attempts have been made to
33 simulate the global DMS distributions, the first of which was introduced in 1999 by interpolating
34 existing surface observations to generate monthly maps of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution⁵. Twelve years
35 later, improved monthly DMS global maps were created using about three times the number of data
36 points as the initial version⁶. For a decade, most atmospheric investigations used these maps⁶ as a
37 reference product for DMS emissions. Recently, the DMS climatology maps have been updated
38 once more⁷, referred to as DMS-Rev3, with a roughly 18-fold increase in the raw database as
39 compared to the second version⁶ which results in more realistic monthly DMS estimates than the
40 previous releases. Concurrently, empirical algorithms were developed to model DMS distributions
41 as a function of controlling parameters like the ratios of chlorophyll-a concentration (CHL) to
42 mixed layer depth (MLD)⁸, solar radiation dose⁹, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), and
43 satellite-based Dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP) concentrations^{10,11}, the major precursor of
44 marine DMS. Detailed information on the existing DMS retrieval algorithms can be found in Ref.
45 [12].

46 Machine learning (ML) algorithms have been applied to create climatological DMS fields that have
47 the advantage of capturing nonlinear interactions between environmental variables and DMS
48 concentrations. Wang et al.¹³ employed artificial neural networks (ANN) for constructing global
49 monthly climatology of DMS maps at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution, hereafter referred to as W20.
50 Although global DMS products are believed to be acceptable for qualitatively describing seasonal
51 variations in DMS^{7,13}, their predictive ability tends to diminish at regional scales, failing to
52 precisely resolve the oceanic mesoscale and sub-mesoscale spatial patterns or shorter temporal scale
53 variability^{12,14-17}. As a result, there is significant uncertainty in the regional distributions of DMS
54 concentration and fluxes amongst various global products¹⁸ owing to the limited space resolution.

55 Regionally, the monthly DMS climatology in the northeast Pacific Ocean was reconstructed at a
56 higher spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ using random forest regression and ANN¹⁷. The study
57 concluded that DMS patterns are linked to mesoscale oceanic variability; such patterns would have
58 remained obscure in the coarser resolution products¹². In terms of temporal coverage, climatology
59 maps cannot properly analyze present and future DMS emission trends under global climate change
60 scenarios^{12,19}. Addressing this issue, Mansour et al.¹² generated the first grided daily time series of
61 DMS concentrations and associated F_{DMS} at a spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. The dataset was

62 generated for the North Atlantic using the GPR model. The DMS time series made it possible to
63 elucidate high-frequency spatial and temporal patterns in DMS variability, proving the usefulness of
64 a cutting-edge technique (GPR) for predicting sea surface DMS concentration and flux. Finding
65 trustworthy high-resolution DMS concentration data is essential since changes in DMS dynamics
66 usually take place on the days-to-week timescales associated with meteorological forcing¹⁶. Another
67 advantage of the improved derived sea-to-air F_{DMS} time series is that it can be utilized to predict and
68 comprehend the dynamics of marine-derived biogenic sulfur aerosol concentrations and their
69 radiative effects²⁰. Furthermore, carrying out relevant scientific studies aiming at reducing aerosol-
70 cloud interaction uncertainty in climate models requires long-term, continuous, and high
71 spatiotemporal resolution datasets.

72 The Mediterranean (MED) Sea, the object of this study, represents one of the most complex marine
73 ecosystems on the planet²¹, with varied physical and chemical processes occurring at different
74 space-time scales such as deep-water formation, thermohaline circulation, and subbasin gyres. MED
75 has been categorized as an oligotrophic basin²² due to the typically low primary production, with
76 notable bio-regionalization in phytoplankton biomass and abundance at the subbasin to regional
77 scales^{23,24}. Although biogenic sulfate aerosol contributes significantly to the sulfur burden in the
78 MED atmosphere (estimated at more than 26%)²⁵⁻²⁷ which is contributed by extensive urban
79 pollution sources surrounding the basin as well as from ship traffic, scarce information is available
80 on the spatio-temporal distribution of seawater DMS concentration and, particularly, sea-to-air flux.
81 Previous findings based on short-term observations revealed that the MED sea, like most of the
82 oligotrophic basins, presents the so-called summer DMS paradox^{28,29} (elevated summer DMS
83 concentrations coupled to low surface CHL levels). DMS production in the MED sea is irradiance-
84 dependent^{30,31} and is not proportional to total phytoplankton biomass^{32,33}. Essentially, the DMS
85 concentrations peak 1-2 months after CHL³³, following phytoplankton succession^{34,35} in stressed
86 cells or grazing-derived production^{36,37}, as well as physiological adjustments^{31,38}.

87 The study aims to assess the plausibility of applying the GPR model, which has been successfully
88 applied in the North Atlantic ocean¹², to predict long-term (1998-2020) high-resolution gridded
89 fields of daily DMS and F_{DMS} time-series covering the MED domain at $0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$ (grid cell
90 area between 60 to 74 km²) spatial resolution. Moreover, it evaluates how well the nested cross-
91 validation performs while evaluating ML models with few observations. A comparison with
92 currently available DMS climatology products has been conducted to show the uncertainty level of
93 their distributions over the regional seas. We explain the seasonal patterns of the predicted DMS
94 and F_{DMS} and how they follow the long-term measurements of MSA, a biogenic aerosol component
95 of DMS oxidation. After evaluating the most popular ML regression models (Table 1 of Ref. [²⁰]),
96 GPR was shown to be the best-performing model for reconstructing DMS observations. The model

97 was built employing the available in-situ sea surface DMS concentrations^{5,16} (Fig. S1), high-
98 resolution satellite observations of CHL, sea surface temperature (SST), and PAR as well as sea
99 surface salinity (SSS) and MLD from the novel MED physical reanalysis³⁹. To gain a better
100 understanding of the links between these parameters and both DMS and F_{DMS} at different time
101 scales, the spatio-temporal variations of these parameters were investigated over 23 years by
102 performing the empirical orthogonal function (EOF) analysis⁴⁰ on the daily gridded datasets.

103 2. Results

104 2.1 GPR Evaluation and Data Generation

105 Using the 5-fold nested cross-validation (nCV) approach (see Methods), we assess the GPR model
106 on test subsets of the outer loop (Fig. 1a). The aim is to minimize overfitting and ensure that the
107 trained/cross-validated model can be adapted to another dataset impartially. Fig. 1b presents the
108 scatter plot between observed and predicted seawater DMS concentrations by GPR. The average
109 evaluation measures, on the 5 test folds, exhibit that GPR achieves a coefficient of determination
110 (R^2) of 0.71 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.12. Notably, the model performance is
111 impartial across the various inner cross-validation subsets, with an R^2 ranging from 0.63 to 0.72 and
112 an RMSE between 0.12 and 0.14 (Fig. S2). The performance is consistent with the results given by
113 the GPR over the North Atlantic domain ($R^2 = 0.71$ and RMSE = 0.21; on the test fold)¹², by
114 implementing nearly four times as many data points in building the model. Contextually, previous
115 studies reported similar prediction performances by using ANN to estimate the monthly climatology
116 of global ocean DMS distributions ($R^2 = 0.66$)¹³ and to characterize spatio-temporal DMS
117 variability in the Yellow and East China Sea ($R^2 = 0.71$)⁴¹. The random forest regression and ANN
118 caught up to 62% of the observed monthly climatology of seawater DMS fluctuation in the
119 northeast subarctic Pacific¹⁷.

120 We compared the GPR model as a tool to predict seawater DMS concentrations with the previously
121 published empirical methods⁸⁻¹⁰ and the ANN¹³ of W20. We adapted an ANN model with the same
122 hyperparameters as W20 (*i.e.*, one input layer, two hidden layers, one output layer, and a regulation
123 parameter value of 0.001) keeping the same potential predictors used in GPR, for proper
124 comparison. The results (Fig. 1c) show that GPR has much higher prediction accuracy with a
125 markedly higher R^2 value and lower mean absolute error (MAE). GPR achieves MAE of $0.52 \mu\text{mol}$
126 m^{-3} , which is 59% lower than the most skilled empirical method⁸, MAE = $1.26 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$, and 7%
127 lower than ANN, MAE = $0.56 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$. This indicates a major improvement in the representation
128 of the regional seawater DMS variability in the MED sea by GPR. The trained GPR model was
129 used to calculate daily seawater DMS concentrations (Fig. 2a), as well as sea-to-air F_{DMS} (Fig. 3a),

130 at each pixel of the MED domain. The gridded data has a high-resolution of $0.083^{\circ} \times 0.083^{\circ}$
131 covering from 1998 to 2020. As an illustration of the data product, Fig. 3b presents a daily time
132 series of DMS and F_{DMS} averaged over the entire MED domain.

133 The annual mean climatological distribution of DMS (Fig. 2a) across the 23-year study period
134 shows that GPR-DMS values vary from 1.68 to $4.39 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$ (minimum and maximum over all
135 the grids), with median value equal to $3.18 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$. In general, DMS concentrations are higher in
136 the eastern Mediterranean (EMED) than in the western Mediterranean (WMED). The south-central
137 Mediterranean (CMED), front of Libyan coast, and the northeast Levantine basin have the highest
138 DMS concentrations. The north Adriatic (at the mouth of the PO river) and north Aegean (near the
139 Sea of Marmara) have the lowest DMS concentrations, which could be attributed to fresh- and low-
140 saline water discharge into the MED. Laboratory-controlled experiments showed that the DMS
141 accumulation rate is reduced as salinity decreases⁴²⁻⁴⁵. The Alboran subbasin, which is near the
142 Gibraltar Strait and is affected by the input of Atlantic water, is another area displaying low DMS
143 concentrations. In comparison to recent estimates of annual climatology from global products (Rev3
144 and W20)^{7,13}, it is noticed that their output failed to resolve DMS spatial variations at regional
145 scales, as expected due to their coarser resolution. The gradual increase in DMS from WMED to
146 EMED can be somewhat represented by the W20, but Rev3 regarded the MED domain as a bulk
147 region where DMS presents reduced spatial variability or almost constant concentrations (Fig. 2 &
148 Fig. S3). Concerning the average concentrations across the MED, the GPR-DMS has an annual
149 mean of $3.14 \pm 0.32 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$, which is comparable with Rev3 ($3.61 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$) and twice as
150 high as W20 ($1.75 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{mol m}^{-3}$). On an annual basis, GPR shows an approximate 13% decrease
151 in DMS concentration compared to Rev3 (Fig. 2d) but is 81% greater than W20 (Fig. 2e),
152 throughout the whole domain.

153 The MED sea-to-air F_{DMS} (Fig. 3a) is calculated to be $4.6 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ on an annual basis;
154 similarly to the DMS distribution, significant regional differences have been observed, primarily the
155 contrasting emissions between the WMED (relatively low emissions) and EMED (high emission
156 rates). The integrated F_{DMS} -derived sulfur emissions over the whole domain have an average of
157 $265.6 \pm 7.6 \text{ Gg yr}^{-1}$, displaying notable interannual variability (Fig. 3b), with the largest flux
158 recorded in 2016 (279.9 Gg) and the minimum flux occurred in 2004 (250.4 Gg). Such an average
159 integrated flux is approximately 12% lower and 58% greater than Rev3 (301.6 Gg yr^{-1}) and W20
160 (168.4 Gg yr^{-1}) climatologies, respectively. It should be mentioned that the estimates of F_{DMS} from
161 the aforementioned global products were computed using the same GPR- F_{DMS} parameterization
162 method⁴⁶ because different approaches produced different results (see Discussion). This was done
163 by using the monthly DMS concentrations (Rev3 and W20) and climatic monthly of SST and WS.

164 This is required to conduct a proper comparison of GPR- F_{DMS} and other estimates, throughout the
165 present study.

166 2.2 Monthly DMS and F_{DMS} distributions

167 In this section, we investigate the monthly climatology of DMS and F_{DMS} from GPR and compare
168 them with the Rev3 and W20 products. The maps are presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. S4. With spring
169 being a season of growth and autumn being a season of decay, the monthly mean sea surface DMS
170 concentrations averaged over the years 1998–2020 (Fig. 4a) exhibit an evident seasonality
171 minimum in winter (Dec to Feb) and maximum in summer (Jun–Jul). The EMED is characterized
172 throughout the year by rather higher values than the WMED. It is observed that the spatial features
173 of the DMS concentration in the oligotrophic MED sea do not match the distribution of CHL, a
174 tracer of phytoplankton activity (Fig. S5) in agreement with previously reported observations^{32,47}.
175 We found that W20 underestimates the DMS concentration, particularly in spring and summer,
176 when compared to GPR. Rev3 quantitatively displays very comparable DMS concentrations,
177 however there is high overestimation in May and inconsistent low values in July (Fig. S4).

178 GPR- F_{DMS} monthly maps (Fig. 4b) show that the main seasonal cycle of DMS flux depends strongly
179 on the seawater concentrations; GPR- F_{DMS} begin to rise in May and peaks in July, followed by a
180 steady decline in September. December and January have the lowest GPR- F_{DMS} at roughly 2.1 ± 0.6
181 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$, while July has the largest emission rate at $8.3 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$. According to the
182 Rev3- F_{DMS} monthly maps (Fig. 4c), F_{DMS} peaks in May ($9.3 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$), two months before
183 GPR, with an incidental dip in July, followed by an increase in August; nonetheless, the minimum
184 levels occur in January ($1.3 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$). The W20- F_{DMS} (Fig. 4d), on the other hand, follows
185 a regular seasonal cycle, with the lowest emission rate in January ($0.8 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) and the
186 highest in August ($3.8 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$). The differences (Rev3-GPR) in F_{DMS} maps (Fig. 4e)
187 show irregular positive and negative values, with positive differences peaking in May ($3.3 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$
188 d^{-1}) and negative differences peaking in July ($-2.0 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$). On the contrary, (W20-GPR)
189 F_{DMS} climatology (Fig. 4d) shows lower values throughout the year, with the greatest discrepancies
190 observed from May to July (up to $-6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ in certain areas of the MED domain) as
191 displayed in Fig. 4f.

192 These findings highlight the discrepancies between global products when estimating DMS emission
193 flux on the regional scale. One shortcoming of both products (Rev3 and W20) is the horizontal
194 resolution ($1^\circ \times 1^\circ$), which pre-supposes that DMS remains constant across each grid area of the
195 domain (between 8.8×10^3 and $10.7 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^2$, in the case of the MED sea). This may be inconsistent
196 with the MED sea's subbasin scale, mesoscale gyres, semi-enclosed nature, complex morphology
197 and coastlines, and a wide range of physical and chemical processes that govern its productivity^{23,48}.

198 In terms of quantitative estimation of the DMS-derived sulfur aerosol budget, while the Rev3
199 product misses a large portion of grids over the Adriatic Sea, the W20 output provides DMS values
200 over the majority of Italy's land area (Fig. 2), indicating a major problem with data quality at the
201 regional scale.

202 2.3 EOF and drivers of DMS and F_{DMS} variabilities

203 The preceding discussions show that DMS and F_{DMS} , retrieved by GPR, display a wide
204 spatiotemporal variability in the MED sea. Herein, the EOF analysis is applied to the gridded high-
205 resolution dataset to investigate the DMS and F_{DMS} spatial variability patterns and how they change
206 with time. Then, to better understand the probable interactions between them and their independent
207 controllers at different space-time scales. The EOF analysis is one of the most extensively used
208 methods for understanding spatio-temporal variability in oceanic and atmospheric data^{40,49}. It allows
209 us to identify the dominant modes of variability by decomposing the dataset into spatial modes
210 (EOF modes that show the patterns of variability) and their associated time series or principal
211 components (PCs), which quantifies the importance of each mode. The findings of the first three
212 EOF modes, where the majority of the variance is explained, for DMS and F_{DMS} , as well as the
213 governing parameters (CHL, MLD, SST, PAR, SSS, WS, and K_{DMS}), were evaluated in the present
214 study. We applied the EOF analysis to the original daily time series during 1998-2020, in order to
215 account for the main cycles of the studied parameters.

216 The spatial patterns of EOF modes and the normalized climatology (during 1998-2020) of their
217 amplitude time series (PCs) for DMS and F_{DMS} are displayed in Fig. 5a-d. The original PCs time
218 series are presented in Fig. S6. The first three EOF modes of the DMS (F_{DMS}) account for about
219 93.7% (64.8%) of the overall variance of the data, with the first mode (EOF1) alone explaining
220 about 90% (50%). In parallel, the EOF1 of CHL, MLD, SST, PAR, SSS, WS, and K_{DMS} accounts
221 for 56.4%, 77.8%, 95.8%, 83.7%, 22.4%, 33.2% and 29.2% of the variance, respectively (Fig. S7-
222 S9).

223 The spatial patterns of EOF1 for DMS (Fig. 5a) and F_{DMS} (Fig. 5b) are positive throughout the
224 MED domain, indicating an in-phase oscillation of the entire basin around the steady-state mean.
225 This indicates the cycle crest emerges when the PC time series is positive too, and vice versa. The
226 Tyrrhenian Sea and the north-central part of the basin including the Adriatic have the largest DMS
227 annual amplitude, whereas the Alboran Sea, South Levantine, and the northernmost part of the
228 Aegean Sea have the lowest variability. Besides, F_{DMS} displays the highest variability in the
229 northwest part of the basin and the Aegean Sea, to the east of Crete Island. The PC1 time series
230 (Fig. S6) and their normalized climatology during 1998-2020 of DMS (Fig. 5c) and F_{DMS} (Fig. 5d)
231 show a clear annual cycle that is the leading component of variabilities. The subbasins showing

232 higher EOF1 values are therefore characterized by a seasonal DMS cycle of greater amplitude. The
233 maximum temporal amplitude is reached in June and July and the minimum in winter (Dec-Feb).
234 The annual cycle of DMS is driven mainly by the available radiation for photosynthesis ($r=0.93$;
235 $p<0.05$ between PC1-DMS and PC1-PAR) (Fig. 5e & Fig. S10). When low CHL and a shallow
236 mixed layer coexist with increased PAR, it suggests that high DMS concentrations are linked to
237 stressed phytoplankton cells stuck in a shallow surface mixing layer due to oxidative stress brought
238 on by irradiance. Contextually, F_{DMS} seasonality is mainly governed by the seawater DMS
239 concentrations ($r=0.89$; $p<0.05$; Fig. S11).

240 The DMS EOF2 mode accounts for around 3.1% of the overall variance. Its spatial pattern is a
241 dipole, with opposite fluctuation between the EMED and WMED (plus Adriatic) subbasins.
242 According to the DMS PC2 climatology, there are two peaks: a point of maximum by the end of
243 April and a peak from end of August to start of September; there are also two troughs: a sharp
244 minimum by the end of June and a broader minimum from January to February. Consequently,
245 high-frequency variations in DMS peaked primarily in late spring and late summer in the EMED,
246 simultaneously, the Adriatic and WMED seas show minimum amplitudes. The peak in late spring
247 may correspond to phytoplankton succession occurring 1-2 months after the late winter and early
248 spring bloom^{34,35}. A possible interpretation of the second peak is that warm EMED water masses
249 may induce DMS production driven by stratification-stressed effects at high surface irradiance. This
250 can be evidenced by the consistency between DMS-EOF2 and SST-EOF2 (Fig. S8) spatial patterns
251 as well as the considerable association between their PCs time series (Fig. S10; $r=-0.37$; $p<0.05$,
252 being the negative sign due to the opposite spatial modes). In parallel, the EOF2 of F_{DMS} explains
253 roughly 9.7% of the variance and divides the MED Sea into two regions with opposing phases. On
254 one side, the central part along the Sicily channel, the Tyrrhenian subbasin, and the northwest
255 section of the MED show relatively high F_{DMS} in May-June. The Levantine and Aegean subbasins,
256 on the other side, exhibit an increase in emissions during August.

257 The DMS EOF3 mode accounts for a minor percentage of the variance (0.8%) and will not be
258 discussed. Conversely, the F_{DMS} EOF3 accounts for about 5.3% of the total variance and its spatial
259 distribution shows an out-of-phase oscillation with opposite peaks between the central part of the
260 basin and the westernmost and easternmost parts of the basin. The maximum variability (with
261 opposed phases) is observed in the Gulf of Lion and the central part of the basin. The variations of
262 PC2 and PC3 of the F_{DMS} time series (Fig. S6 & Fig. 5d) are characterized by high-frequency
263 oscillations (low periods; of the order of days). Such small-time scale variations of F_{DMS} can be
264 driven by changes in wind speed and consequently, the DMS gas transfer velocity (K_{DMS}). This can
265 be seen clearly from the positive correlation between PC2- F_{DMS} and both PC2-WS ($r=0.67$;
266 $p<0.05$) and PC2- K_{DMS} ($r=0.70$; $p<0.05$) as well as a similar relationship between the PC3 time

267 series of these components (Fig. S11). It is worthwhile to point out that the Gulf of Lion is
268 vulnerable to strong short-term wind events (e.g., the Mistral wind⁵⁰) which contribute to enhanced
269 air-sea interactions⁵¹.

270 In summary, the EOF analysis shows that the annual fluctuation is the leading component of DMS
271 variability over the MED sea, captured by EOF1; such a component is driven mainly by physical
272 conditions like the available solar radiation. Variations on a smaller time scale contribute to a minor
273 part of the variability and occur with opposite phases in the western and eastern parts of the domain.

274 Also, the variability of F_{DMS} is mostly driven by the yearly cycle, even though the magnitude of the
275 variation is lower than that of DMS concentration whilst EOF 2 and 3 are relatively more important
276 for F_{DMS} than for DMS. The main driver of the yearly fluctuations in F_{DMS} is the seawater DMS
277 concentration. Local winds seem to play an important role in the F_{DMS} short-term scale fluctuations
278 over the MED sea, as highlighted in EOF2 and EOF3. Supporting that, the F_{DMS} monthly
279 distributions (Fig. 4b) show a hotspot of high emission rates over the Aegean Sea (an area of low
280 DMS concentrations) during summer (the season of low wind). This could be due to the impact of
281 the intensified Etesian winds blowing over the Aegean Sea during summer⁵². This can be observed
282 in the monthly fields of wind climatology (1998-2020) presented in Fig. S12.

283 **2.4 F_{DMS} and MSA relationship: potential perspectives**

284 The study's outcomes provide an inventory of marine biogenic DMS emissions that can be used to
285 improve the modeling of biogenic sulfur aerosol concentrations²⁰ in the MED atmosphere. To
286 investigate this possibility, we compare high-resolution constructed GPR- F_{DMS} with atmospheric
287 particulate methanesulfonic acid (MSA) concentrations in background marine conditions. The MSA
288 measurements were carried out at Lampedusa (see Methods), a central MED site (Fig. S1), from
289 2005 to 2019. A subset of the available MSA samples was chosen to represent atmospheric marine
290 boundary layer conditions in the MED, hence limiting continental and/or anthropogenic
291 contamination. This was accomplished, according to the back-trajectory analysis (Section 4.4, Fig.
292 S13 and Fig. S14), by selecting samples synchronized only to air masses with a high degree of
293 interaction with seawater when passing through the MED domain.

294 Fig. 6a shows the scatter plot between the observed MSA at Lampedusa and the GPR- F_{DMS}
295 averaged inside the box area comprising grid coordinates 32°-42° N and 05°-20° E (black box in
296 Fig. S1). This black box area has the potential to be the main source region of biogenic emissions
297 arriving at the sampling point during the entire measuring period (2005-2019), revealed by air mass
298 frequency analysis. There is a significant correlation ($r=0.57$; $p<0.05$) between GPR- F_{DMS} and
299 MSA atmospheric concentration. The link is mostly driven by seasonality, with low F_{DMS} synced to
300 low MSA concentrations in the winter (Dec-Feb), and a substantial increase in both parameters

301 during summer (Jun-Aug). During the period 2005-2019, the summer average [median] MSA
302 concentration was about 38.3 ± 22.5 [34.3] ng m^{-3} , about 10 orders of magnitude higher than the
303 concentration levels in winter (3.6 ± 2.9 [2.9] ng m^{-3}). Simultaneously to MSA concentration, F_{DMS}
304 increased from 2.1 ± 0.7 [2.0] $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ in winter to 7.0 ± 2.0 [6.7] $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ in summer
305 (nearly three times stronger emissions). Apart from the seasonal minima and maxima, F_{DMS}
306 emissions and MSA concentration are very consistent also during the transition seasons of autumn
307 and spring.

308 The seasonal changes were examined (Fig. 6b) and compared to those calculated using previously
309 published F_{DMS} climatologies (Rev3 and W20). The seasonal trend of MSA concentrations shows
310 peaks in the summer (Jun-Jul) and declines in the winter (Dec-Feb). This tendency aligns with the
311 seasonal fluctuations in GPR- F_{DMS} , emphasizing the importance of high-resolution datasets in
312 representing the real atmosphere and improving the simulation of DMS-derived aerosols and their
313 associated radiative impacts. Conversely, the Rev3- F_{DMS} peak appears earlier (in May) than the
314 MSA concentration peak, while the W20- F_{DMS} peak appears later (in September), and they are
315 generally less consistent with the MSA seasonal trend (Fig. 6b) compared to GPR.

316 **3. Discussion**

317 DMS, as the main oceanic source of sulfur aerosol particles in the atmosphere, can affect regional
318 and global climate via altering cloud condensation nuclei concentrations. However, it is not
319 effectively represented in climate models, particularly across regional seas, because precisely
320 predicting the sea-to-air F_{DMS} is challenging. The capacity to capture high-frequency spatial and
321 temporal patterns in DMS and F_{DMS} variations is one of the advantages of generating high-
322 resolution data products. The limited performance of previous methods at fine regional scales is
323 becoming increasingly apparent globally^{12,15,17}. This undoubtedly encourages the scientific
324 community to focus on fine-scale regional parameterizations.

325 In the present work, the GPR model predicts seawater DMS with superior performance than
326 previously published methods, capturing 71% of daily variations on completely different
327 independent test subsets. However, the applied model and the previously published ML methods
328 still struggle to capture high and low DMS concentrations^{13,14,17}. Such extreme values are scarce but
329 important considering their potential role in radiative forcing. ML algorithms normally assume
330 uniform distributions, although the majority of oceanic and atmospheric datasets have skewed
331 distributions, with certain values within specific ranges occurring less frequently. As a result,
332 models perform better for frequently represented data points than for rare extremes. In addition,
333 during model training, a group of predictors may dominate because of their strong match with the
334 response, whilst other less-weighted predictors may play a role in shaping extreme values. It will

335 take more research to overcome this challenge to use ML more effectively in oceanic and
336 atmospheric studies.

337 The major concern that can arise about the proposed dataset regards the limited number of
338 observations available to train the GPR model. A detailed discussion on the suitability of the in-situ
339 DMS concentration dataset for the purpose of training the GPR model can be found in the
340 Supplementary material (Text S1, Fig. S15-S18). Here, we stress out that GPR does not work by
341 interpolating the observations in space or time; instead, it derives a relation between the predicted
342 variable and the considered predictors, using then said relation to re-construct the predicted variable
343 outside the training domain, as a function of the measured predictors. For this reason, GPR cannot
344 be reasonably affected by anomalous observations (*i.e.*, observations not representative of the
345 climatological conditions) that might be non-negligible in a small dataset, as far as the relation
346 between predicted variable and predictors remain consistent. This condition is evidently respected
347 in the training dataset used here, as shown by the good performance of the model to reconstruct the
348 observations. If anomalous observations had distorted or disrupted the DMS vs. predictors
349 relationship, the model would have failed in evidencing such relationship, resulting in a low or null
350 prediction performance.

351 The most typical technique to validate a ML model is to keep a separate subset of the data for
352 testing in parallel to the using the normal CV on the training subset^{12,20}. However, this method
353 demands enough amount of data to apply the train/test split and exclude the test subset from the
354 model building up. Rather than testing the model only once, many models can be tested iteratively
355 on different portions of the data utilizing the nCV. The nCV allows to train and test a model many
356 times with non-overlapping subsets. This strategy is specifically designed to work with a limited
357 number of data points and to determine whether the model can produce unbiased performance on
358 different test subsets. A potential benefit of the nCV is that it uses all of the available data for model
359 training and testing, which should produce results that are more representative of the data
360 population than using only a portion of the data, as with a train/test split or new dataset. Because the
361 nCV adds significantly more information to the model to learn from it, the method can be used even
362 when there is ample data.

363 Based on the ML evidenced relation between DMS concentration and the driving predictors
364 employed, the model has been extended to run over non-sampled areas for constructing the
365 presenting datasets. We underline that for running GPR on a new dataset it is not important to
366 achieve an extensive time or space data coverage in the training dataset, but instead to cover a
367 significant fraction of the DMS and predictors variabilities, which was achieved in this study as
368 shown in Fig. S17. The time frame used in the GPR development is 1999-2012, and the model is
369 used to predict from 1998-2020. The capacity to evaluate the robustness of the model's performance

370 over time is limited by the availability of seawater DMS data, emphasizing the importance of doing
371 more observations in regional waters and overlooked seas. Nevertheless, the correlation between
372 MSA measurements and the predicted F_{DMS} provide confidence that the GPR is picking up the
373 prominent patterns. Interestingly, the F_{DMS} -MSA relationship remained unchanged between the
374 training period of 2005–2012 and the extension period of 2013–2019, when no DMS measurements
375 were accessible (Fig. S18), confirming that the DMS concentration and related fluxes were not
376 biased by the GPR algorithm when operating outside the training period.

377 It is vital to highlight that the sea-to-air F_{DMS} is predominantly determined by seawater DMS
378 concentration, with DMS gas transfer velocity acting as another regulator (EOF analysis). The
379 choice of the parametrization method of gas transfer velocity impacts the F_{DMS} quantification. We
380 used the Blomquist et al.⁴⁶ method, which yields the best match with the MSA (Fig. S19) and is
381 suggested by Bhatti et al.⁵³ study. However, we report that the use of Goddijn-Murphy et al.⁵⁴ and
382 Nightingale et al.⁵⁵ parametrizations provided higher F_{DMS} by around 18% and 28%, respectively,
383 compared to Blomquist et al.⁴⁶, evaluated over the MED domain on an annual basis (Fig. S20).

384 The improved dataset outperforms previous offerings in terms of describing mesoscale
385 spatiotemporal variability of DMS concentration and sea-to-air flux; this essential dataset is
386 imperative for long-term studies on marine aerosol and the assessment of its radiative impacts in
387 climate models. Importantly, the GPR model can capture the summer DMS paradox (EOF analysis),
388 which is a characteristic phenomenon of most of the oligotrophic basins. The CHL in the MED sea,
389 as a proxy of phytoplankton activity, do not follow the DMS and MSA concentrations seasonal
390 trend, evidence of the complexity of the MED biogeochemical cycle³¹. This is most likely due to the
391 various mechanisms that contribute to the breakdown of phytoplankton cells and the release of
392 DMS, as well as DMS emission into the atmosphere and oxidation to MSA. When biological
393 activity is at its peak in late winter and early spring due to MED general circulation and deep-water
394 formation and the solar radiation has not yet reached its peak in the summer, DMS release is still
395 modest. When solar radiation reaches its maximum in summer, DMS and F_{DMS} tend to be
396 maximized accordingly. In essence, in warm-oligotrophic environments like the MED sea, the
397 annual cycle appears to be considerably more linked to physical parameters (e.g., solar radiation
398 and surface temperature), whereas biotic variables contribute to quick (high frequency) DMS
399 adjustments. The fact that GPR is able to reconstruct such complex interactions between DMS
400 concentration and its predictors contributes to building confidence on the reliability of the modeled
401 dataset.

402 Notwithstanding the above pieces of evidence supporting the general reliability of the modeled
403 DMS concentration fields, we cannot rule out some degree of uncertainty due to the limited space-
404 time coverage of DMS observations in the MED basin. For instance, we evidence that no

405 measurements were available for the Adriatic Sea and therefore we invite future users to be careful
406 when extrapolating DMS data for such area, considering its enclosed nature and oceanographic
407 peculiarity.

408 As an effective tool for predicting DMS, as demonstrated in this study and the previous one in the
409 North Atlantic¹², GPR can be run in different biogeochemical provinces of the global ocean⁵⁶, to
410 produce much more reliable products with high spatial resolutions. This necessitates global
411 advances in physical ocean reanalysis as well. Enhanced global oceanic products have the potential
412 to significantly improve the simulation of aerosols originating from DMS even in marine regions
413 with complex morphology and dynamics as well as the resulting regional-scale aerosol-cloud
414 interaction effects.

415 According to both present and future projections, the MED is a hotspot for global warming because
416 its changes have been more rapid than those of the ocean as a whole⁵⁷, having a significant effect
417 and increasing risks on all sectors of the marine environment during the coming decades⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰.

418 Reliable representations of marine biogenic emissions, as well as their long-term variations and
419 future scenarios in the context of climate change, are among the key products to reduce aerosol-
420 cloud interaction uncertainty in MED regional climate models.

421 **4. Methods**

422 **4.1 Study Domain and Data Sources**

423 Our research domain is the MED Sea, extending from 30° to 46° N and from 06° W to 36.5° E (Fig.
424 S1). Geographically, it is divided into three major subbasins: the Western Basin (WMED), which is
425 connected to the Atlantic Ocean by the Strait of Gibraltar, the Central Basin (CMED), which
426 encompasses the Sicily Channel, the Ionian Sea, and the Adriatic Sea, and the Western basin
427 (WMED), which is connected to the Black Sea by the Dardanelles Strait and the Sea of Marmara.
428 The datasets used for this study are retrieved from satellite products, in-situ data, and model
429 reanalysis in the period 1998–2020. The datasets for this research were obtained from high-
430 resolution satellite products and the Mediterranean Sea Physics Reanalysis. They are briefly
431 described below:

- 432 • Daily Level4 (L4) chlorophyll-a concentration (CHL) taken from Copernicus-GlobColour
433 Satellite Observations at 0.042°×0.042° resolutions.
- 434 • Daily photosynthetically available radiation (PAR) data were collected from NASA Ocean
435 Color products such as SeaWiFS (1998-2002), MODIS-Terra (2001-2021), and MODIS-
436 Aqua (2003-2021). SeaWiFS has a spatial resolution of 9 km (0.083°×0.083°), while

437 MODIS has a resolution of 4 km ($0.042^\circ \times 0.042^\circ$); both are L3 outputs. The data were
438 merged and linearly interpolated before being processed as L4 data.

- 439 • The L4 daily SST fields^{61,62} were generated by the EU Copernicus Marine Environment
440 Monitoring Service (CMEMS) using satellite estimates, with $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ spatial resolution.
- 441 • The daily sea surface salinity (SSS) and mixed layer depth (MLD) were taken from the
442 MED Sea physical reanalysis at $1/24^\circ \times 1/24^\circ$ resolution³⁹. This data is a multiyear output
443 generated by a numerical system comprised of a hydrodynamic model and a variational data
444 assimilation method developed in the CMEMS framework.

445 In addition, in-situ observations of surface seawater DMS concentrations were obtained from the
446 Global Surface Seawater DMS Database (Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory, PMEL⁵) in the
447 MED sea domain and from Royer et al.¹⁶ campaigns. The sampling points are shown in Fig. S1. All
448 the data including DMS, the aforementioned satellite data and physical reanalysis data were binned
449 into $0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$ (~ 9 km) daily resolution. The binned dataset was used in the training and nCV
450 validation of the GPR model.

451 4.2 GPR training and the nested cross-validation

452 We built up the GPR model using the daily binned ($0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$) independent variables (features)
453 as predictors of seawater DMS concentrations. The predictors are CHL, SST, PAR, MLD, SSS, and
454 the day of year (DOY). The use of DOY as a temporal predictor seeks to compensate for the lack of
455 data continuity in observations. GPR^{12,20} is an efficient ML algorithm that solves regression
456 problems using a non-parametric kernel-based Bayesian probabilistic strategy⁶³. It is powerful on
457 small datasets since contemporary kernel (covariance) functions are readily available⁶⁴. The kernel
458 function used in this study is the exponential that has been defined as the best optimal one in
459 predicting DMS¹² in a previous attempt. In the MED domain, a total of 402 remapped data points,
460 jointly obtained from cruises and fixed stations (Fig. S1). After transforming to the log- scale, of the
461 402 data points, we eliminated two points that lie below the threshold (mean – three times the
462 standard deviation) and three points that lie above the threshold (mean + three times the standard
463 deviation), which can be considered outliers. Ultimately, 1.2% of the total points have been
464 eliminated and the rest of data points which equal to 397 were used for the model generation.

465 We evaluated the GPR using the nCV loop to prevent model overfitting and guarantee the unbiased
466 generalization of the trained model (Fig. 1a). In this manner, the dataset is divided into k outer folds
467 approximately of equal size; each outer fold is kept aside for testing, and the remaining k-1 folds are
468 combined and further divided into inner folds for training and cross-validation. We used 5-fold

469 cross-validation in both the inner and outer loops, keeping in mind that the dataset was divided
470 randomly without repetition between the subsets. This means that all the data has been divided into
471 5 folds (each with about 80 points). Each time in the outer loop we select a fold as a test set, while
472 the remaining four folds are used for training. The four folds are divided once more into five groups
473 to apply the standard cross-validation^{12,20} in the inner loop. This procedure will be repeated five
474 times; hence each part of the data will serve as the testing set for once; afterwards, the simulated
475 results when serving as the testing set are aggregated and plotted versus the observed DMS to show
476 the generalization ability of the GPR model. The nCV enables the model to be tested across all
477 independent test subgroups and yield an average performance. The approach is particularly useful in
478 situations when there is a limited amount of data, as in our case, as it enables multiple training and
479 testing of a model utilizing the non-overlapping parts (*i.e.*, folds) of the dataset.

480 The GPR model was used to generate the long-term (1998-2020) gridded fields of high-resolution
481 ($0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$) daily DMS distributions across the MED sea. Consequently, daily sea-to-air F_{DMS}
482 were calculated using seawater DMS concentrations by GPR and the gas transfer velocity (K_{DMS}),
483 which in turn depends on the surface wind speed (WS) and the DMS diffusivity through seawater
484 (Schmidt number; Sc_{DMS}). The K_{DMS} has been parametrized using the following equation of
485 Blomquist et al.⁴⁶:

$$486 \quad K_{DMS} = 0.7432 \times (WS)^{1.352} \times (660/Sc_{DMS})^{1/2}$$

487 The WS is the neutral wind speed at 10 m above the sea surface and has been downloaded from the
488 ECMWF-ERA5 reanalysis dataset⁶⁵. The Sc_{DMS} has been calculated using Saltzman et al.⁶⁶ from
489 SST.

490 **4.3 MSA sampling and analytical determination**

491 The atmospheric particulate MSA concentration sampling was carried out at the Station for Climate
492 Observations, maintained by ENEA (the National Agency for New Technologies, Energy, and
493 Sustainable Economic Development of Italy) at Lampedusa (35.5 °N, 12.6 °E) in the central
494 Mediterranean (Fig. S1). Particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter lower than 10 μm (PM_{10})
495 was sampled during 2005-2019 at 24h time resolution, except the year 2019 which has 48 h time
496 resolution. Detailed description of the applied sampling protocols and analysis methodologies can
497 be found in Becagli et al.³¹.

498 **4.4 Air mass back-trajectories analysis**

499 We analysed the air mass back-trajectories (BTs) to identify the main areas of the MED domain that
500 can act as a source region of biogenic emissions arrived at the Lampedusa measuring site. The BTs
501 were calculated by running the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT4)

502 model. The starting height is set to be 100 m AGL, and the backward time is 3 days with an interval
503 of 1 h along each entire trajectory track. The arrival frequency is 3h (eight tracks per day at 00, 03,
504 06, 09, 12, 15, 18, 21 UTC) covering the period of MSA measurements (2005–2019). The total
505 number of BTs tracks is 43,824 (5478 days \times 8 tracks a day). The frequency of BTs endpoints of all
506 tracks is presented in Fig. S13. This was done by counting the number of endpoints in each
507 $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid cell and normalized them to the maximum value to find the percentage of endpoints
508 for all grid cells.

509 To identify the air mass tracks characterized by a high degree of contact with the MED surface water
510 before arriving at Lampedusa, we calculated two indices: the retention ratio of the air mass over the
511 MED seawater (R_O) and the retention ratio of an ocean air mass within the marine boundary layer
512 (R_B). The R_O values quantify the lifetime of air masses spending over the seawater to the total lifetime
513 whereas, R_B evaluates how such an air mass is confined within the boundary layer height. The
514 boundary layer height datasets at each endpoint were extracted from the hourly ECMWF-ERA5
515 dataset. The approach and equations are described in detail in Mansour et al.²⁰. Ultimately, the marine
516 air masses included in this study are identified if they have $R_O \geq 0.8$ and $(R_O + R_B) \geq 1.3$. In this way,
517 we kept the air mass that had a high degree of contact with the MED surface water within the last 3
518 days before arrival at the Lampedusa site. Fig. S14 displays the frequency of endpoints of the
519 identified marine tracks of the air masses passing across the MED domain. The sea area presenting
520 high marine BTs frequency (more than the 3rd quartile) was identified as the most likely source region
521 of biogenic emissions impacting Lampedusa measured samples during the investigated period (2005-
522 2019). The MSA concentration samples corresponding to marine BTs tracks were selected and
523 compared to DMS flux averaged within this area, delineated by the green box in Fig. S14.

524

525 **Data Availability**

526 The satellite CHL concentrations are available from Copernicus-GlobColour Satellite Observations,
527 accessible at <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00281>. The SST fields were obtained from the
528 Mediterranean Sea - High Resolution L4 Sea Surface Temperature, accessible at
529 <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00173>. The PAR (SeaWiFS, MODIS-Terra, and MODIS-Aqua) were
530 obtained from NASA Ocean Color at <https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov>. The SSS and MLD were
531 obtained from Mediterranean Sea Physics Reanalysis, accessible at
532 https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004_E3R1. The ECMWF
533 ERA5 neutral wind speed data were obtained from <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47>. The
534 DMS observations data are available from <http://saga.pmel.noaa.gov/dms/> and the Royer et al. 2016

535 cruises are obtained from Martí Galí. The MSA measurements at Lampedusa are available based
536 upon request from the corresponding author.

537

538 **Code Availability**

539 The codes used in this study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

540

541 **Acknowledgements**

542 This research has been supported by the European Commission's EU Horizon 2020 Framework
543 program, project FORCeS (grant no. 821205). We gratefully acknowledge the EU Copernicus
544 Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) for the provision of satellite data and
545 Mediterranean physics reanalysis, the Copernicus climate change service (C3S) for providing ERA5
546 reanalysis data, the PMEL project for the observed DMS measurements and the NOAA Air
547 Resources Laboratory (ARL) for the provision of the HYSPLIT transport and dispersion model.
548 Measurements at Lampedusa were partly supported by the Italian Ministry for University and
549 Research through the NextData and Ritmare projects. We thank Damiano Sferlazzo and Francesco
550 Monteleone for the scientific and technical support of the aerosol sampling at Lampedusa. We
551 thank Martí Galí for providing DMS observations and his insightful comments on the results of the
552 manuscript.

553

554 **Author Contributions**

555 KM conceptualized and designed the study. SB provided the MSA data at Lampedusa. KM
556 organized the datasets, constructed the models, analysed the data, and visualized the results. KM
557 wrote the manuscript under the supervision of MR. All authors contributed to the results
558 investigation, manuscript revision, reading and editing and have approved the final version of the
559 manuscript.

560

561 **Competing Interests**

562 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
563 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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767 **Figure 1. The GPR training and validation process.** (a) The nested-cross validation strategy used
768 to evaluate GPR. (b) comparison of predicted and observed seawater DMS by GPR, evaluated on
769 the test folds of the outer loop. (c) comparison between estimated and observed DMS from the
770 previous empirical algorithms and ANN.

771

772 **Figure 2. Annual climatology of seawater DMS concentrations.** (a) spatial distribution of DMS
773 based on the GPR model at $0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$ over 1998–2020. Climatology output at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ based on
774 Rev3 (b) and W20 (c) estimates. Note that the color scale is different for each product. The relative
775 difference of GPR from Rev3 (d) and from W20 (e) as percentages.

776

777 **Figure 3. The sea-to-air F_{DMS} annual climatology and time series.** (a) Annual distribution of
778 F_{DMS} at $0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$ over 1998–2020 derived from the predicted DMS concentrations (GPR) and
779 Blomquist et al.⁴⁶ parametrization. (b) daily time series of average DMS and F_{DMS} in the entire
780 Mediterranean obtained by GPR in 1998–2020, whereas shaded areas represent \pm spatial standard
781 deviations. The black line represents the annual total cumulative emission fluxes (integrated over
782 the area of each pixel in the domain) in Giga grams per year.

783

784 **Figure 4. Monthly spatial distributions of sea surface DMS concentrations and related**
785 **emission flux.** (a) DMS maps based on GPR during 1998–2020, (b–d) sea-to-air F_{DMS} based on the
786 Blomquist et al.⁴⁶ parametrization and the predicted DMS from GPR, Rev3 and W20. (e) the
787 difference between Rev3-based F_{DMS} and GPR-based F_{DMS} . (f) the difference between the W20-
788 based F_{DMS} and GPR-based F_{DMS} . The pixel resolution of (a) and (b) is $0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$ while (c),
789 (d), (e) and (f) have $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolution. The monthly (average \pm spatial standard deviation) is
790 shown in brackets in each panel.

791

792 **Figure 5. EOF analysis.** The first three modes of EOF spatial patterns of (a) DMS and (b) F_{DMS}
793 calculated from daily ($0.083^\circ \times 0.083^\circ$) datasets generated by GPR and their corresponding daily
794 climatology of PCs time series for the 1998–2020 period (c–d). (e–f) daily climatology of PCs time
795 series of the environmental parameters controlling DMS and F_{DMS} . The PCs of each parameter have
796 normalized from -1 to 1. Shaded areas represent \pm standard deviations.

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798

799 **Figure 6. Relationship between F_{DMS} and MSA. (a)** Scatter plot between MSA observed at
800 Lampedusa measuring site (black filled square in **Fig. S1**) and the GPR F_{DMS} averaged inside the
801 box delineated in **Fig. S1**. The F_{DMS} is calculated from the predicted DMS concentrations by GPR
802 employing Blomquist et al.⁴⁶ parametrization. The diamond symbols represent the seasonal median
803 and the whiskers extend to the 1st and 3rd quartiles. **(b)** Monthly box charts of MSA at Lampedusa,
804 each box chart displays the median (line inside of each box), the 1st and 3rd quartiles (bottom and
805 top edges of each box), the mean (connected line), and the climatology of F_{DMS} from different
806 estimates inside the same box area.